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ABOUT IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TEACHING MUSIC LESSONS IN
SECONDARY SCHOOLS**

Annotation: This article talks about methods of forming musical literacy in elementary school students.

Key words: beginning, music, literacy, media, tempo, rhythm.

All the knowledge and concepts given to students about music are included in the scope of music literacy. In particular, as an important type of music art, the ability to express the real reality of life through sounds, its means of expression (language, speech), types of genres, structure, performance styles, types of performance, classification features related to musical instruments constitutes the main composition. In music literacy, starting from musical sounds and their extension, to terms, pace (tempo), method (rhythm), scale, intervals, alteration, dynamic symbols, simple music form, genres, major and minor scales, theoretical an understanding of knowledge is given. Music lessons and musical education are of particular importance in raising the growing young generation to become mature in all aspects. In this regard, it is one of the important tasks of music teachers to focus on the spiritual and educational maturity of elementary school students, especially in the process of teaching singing, to pay attention to the cultivation of artistic creativity. is considered one of the most important tasks. The president of our republic Sh.Mirziyoyev, deeply feeling the possibilities of music culture teachers, i.e. the owners of this profession, paid special attention to the need to provide musical education to the young generation and issued a special decree to create the necessary conditions for them.

It is known that teachers cannot freely analyze a piece of music, or they find it difficult to use the results obtained in the first exercises in the next exercises. They do not understand the connection between singing skills. In such cases, there are many difficulties in the effective course of the lesson and in the quality singing of a particular work. For this reason, it is necessary to use the method of "re-singing exercises" among students. There are 2 terms of this method, both of which are related to each other. Firstly, to have a thorough and accurate knowledge of what exactly to do when the student sings and what positive results can be achieved, and secondly, to know what they have achieved, how each exercise has resulted, as well as what mistakes have been made. is to know. In the next exercises used in this regard, it should be aimed directly at eliminating these mistakes, correcting them, and singing cleanly and clearly. It is known that one of the most important aspects in feeling the descriptive content of music is the combination of chords. Lad (pitch, mode) is a system of interdependence of sounds with different pitches. In order for the students to understand that the musical works are written on the basis of major and minor scales, it is an advantage to explain them with relative words such as bright, bright, cheerful, festive (major), soft, gentle, pleasant, and melodious (minor). is enough. For this, the teacher should explain the importance of the five note paths: the note path is the place where the note is written. As he draws the path of the note on the board, he points to the bottom line, where the counting of the lines begins. It is possible to explain that the notes are written on these lines, between the lines, using the following quatrain. Do, re, mi, fa, sol, lya, si, Lines-note path The writing is in five lines. Interesting for those who know! Long-shortness, high-low notes, key, tonality, partial scales and the place of similar symbols in a melody or song are performed with the help of various interesting games, riddles and rebuses. Teaching the division of notes to students is also important in developing the level of musical knowledge.

First of all, practicing songs familiar to children will help to implement this activity. Naturally, children's ability to sense harmony varies. The exercises are divided into three groups depending on ability, starting from three to four lessons. Individual musical abilities of children can be identified and studied while singing small exercises. Here, the individual characteristics of each student's attitude to music, singing position of the vocal cords, respiratory tract, and pronunciation are meant. For the correct formation of these features, it is appropriate to divide them into three groups. The direct influence of national musical instruments on the positive formation of singing skills is important. Uzbek national musical instruments such as circle, drum, gijjak, tanbur, flute are rarely used in the music lessons of many schools. A perfect knowledge of the importance of national instruments will further increase their interest in learning. So, if these musical instruments are used more, the result of the process of formation of singing skills would be more effective.

REFERENCES:

1. D. Omonullayeva. Darsda xalq merosi o'rganish. Boshlang'ich ta'lim 2003y 2. Laylo Umurzoqova Baxtiyorovna "Роль культуры в человеке и обществе".
2. Taxirovich M. K. UMUM TA'LIM MAKTABNING SINF O'QUVCHILARDA, MUSIQIY SAVODXONLIGINI SHAKLLANTIRISH USULLARI //NIDERLAND" INTEGRATION, EVOLUTION, MODERNIZATION: WAYS OF DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION". – 2023. – Т. 14. – №. 1.
3. Тажимуратова Ш. С. САНЪАТШУНОСЛИК ФАНЛАРИНИ ЎҚИТИШ ОРҚАЛИ ТАЛАБАЛАРНИНГ МУСТАҚИЛ ИШЛАШ КЎНИКМАЛАРИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ. – 2023.
4. Tajimuratova S. FORMATION OF STUDENTS'SKILLS OF INDEPENDENT PERFORMANCE THROUGH THE TEACHING OF ART HISTORY //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 196-203.
5. Saginbaevna T. S. FORMATION OF STUDENTS'SKILLS OF INDEPENDENT PERFORMANCE THROUGH THE TEACHING OF ART HISTORY //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2022. – Т. 9. – С. 386-392.
6. Tajimuraova S. S. INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATIONS IN MANAGEMENT //Journal of Integrated Education and Research. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 509-511.